

The Nearest Black Hole

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Kareem El-Badry (Harvard-CfA; Max Planck IfA) and collaborators have used GMOS on Gemini North to help identify a $9.62 \pm 0.18 M_{\odot}$ black hole (BH) only 480 pc distant. This object, informally designated as Gaia BH1, is now the closest black hole known by a factor of three. Unlike nearly all known ‘stellar-mass’ BHs, that is, those having masses $< 100 M_{\odot}$, Gaia BH1 was not detected by X-ray emission powered by gas accreted from a nearby, tightly bound, stellar companion. It is presently quiescent and was only identified by its astrometric perturbation of a Sun-like star orbiting it at a distance of 1.44 ± 0.11 AU. The large separation of its companion, which is the largest known for a BH/star binary (Figure 1), raises questions as to how the system formed and evolved to its present state. The observations and implications of the discovery of Gaia BH1 are published in El-Badry et al. (2022).

El-Badry and collaborators discovered Gaia BH1 as part of a program to find non-accreting stellar-mass BHs. While several stellar-mass BHs have been found as X-ray binaries,

the very mass-accretion that makes them visible in X-rays poses the question of how much mass has been accreted since the initial formation of such BHs, presumably in the core-collapse of massive stars. Determining the initial mass function of stellar-mass BHs is a crucial test of the final evolution of high-mass stars. Backing out the subsequent mass growth of the BHs in X-ray binaries is an important, but poorly understood correction. Astrometry over the duration of the Gaia mission, however, provides a way to find quiescent non-accreting BHs. El-Badry’s team found six candidates for BHs within a large list of stars showing astrometric evidence for being bound to another object. Follow-up observations show that Gaia BH1, however, is the only candidate in this set for which the star detected by Gaia, apparently an ordinary main-sequence G-dwarf, indeed appears to be orbiting a stellar-mass BH.

Following up the Gaia astrometric observations with radial velocity observations of the G-dwarf was key to accurate determination of its orbit around its BH companion, and in

Figure 1: Mass of the BH vs. orbital period of its stellar companion is plotted for all known BH/stellar binaries. Gaia BH1 is at the right end of the figure, having a companion with the largest orbit of all known BH/stellar binaries. Credit: Figure reproduced from K. El-Badry, et al. (2022).

Figure 2: The radial velocity of the stellar companion of Gaia BH1 is plotted as a function of orbital phase. GMOS observations were critical for the accurate determination of its peri-center passage. *Credit: Figure reproduced from K. El-Badry, et al. (2022).*

turn determination of the BH's mass. Several instruments were used for this, which included GMOS on Gemini North. GMOS observations were made as part of a Director's Discretionary (DD) time program (program ID: GN-2022B-DD-202). The rapid response provided by the DD program was especially valuable as the observations could be timed to observe the peri-center passage of the G dwarf around the BH (Figure 2). With an overall 185.6-day period, this opportunity was available only within a narrow window that occurred every six months. That the central object in the system is indeed a BH is compelling, as while it contains ~90% of the mass of the system, the G-dwarf contributes all the light.

The present configuration of the Gaia BH1 system is difficult to explain under the most common stellar evolution scenarios

considered by El-Badry et al. (2022). While the system did not evolve to produce a tight binary, the present orbit of the G-dwarf would have had it embedded in the envelope of the $> 20 M_{\odot}$ supergiant that would have immediately preceded the formation of the present BH. It is unlikely that the G-dwarf companion could have survived such a 'common envelope' phase. Separately, El-Badry et al. speculate that the proximity of the Gaia BH1 means that quiescent BHs may be common. The discovery of additional systems will show if the formation of Gaia BH1 is, in the end, unusual.

Reference

El-Badry, K., et al. 2022, *MNRAS*, 518, 1057. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac3140>